

STAGES OF FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF ECONOMIC JOURNALISM IN UZBEKISTAN, ITS FUNCTIONS

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Abstract: *This article investigates the role of economic journalism in the Uzbek media landscape, its historical roots, stages of development, and current tasks. Economic journalism is considered one of the leading branches of mass media. Although it is a relatively new field in national journalism, its historical roots can be traced back to the 5th-8th centuries, evident in ancient Turkic written sources such as the Orkhon-Yenisei, Bilge Khagan, and Kül Tigin inscriptions. The article analyzes the views of Uzbek and foreign scholars comparatively, and based on independent research, examines the formation and development of economic journalism in Uzbekistan in four stages, thoroughly investigating its functions and providing scientific recommendations. The relevance of the article lies in its examination, using primary sources, of the previously almost unstudied formation and history of Uzbek economic journalism. It argues that the journalistic school, traditions, and rich experience created during the Jadid press (late 19th century) formed an important foundation for the development of pure economic journalism in the post-independence period. The article concludes by offering scientific suggestions and recommendations for the further development of this branch of journalism, highlighting its novelty.*

Keywords: *journalism; economic journalism; newspaper; magazine; Jadid press; business press; formation of journalism; historical evolution; function.*

Introduction

Journalism is a broad field encompassing numerous types and directions. While their names may vary, their goals and objectives remain consistent: to gather, process, and disseminate information. They differ only in their methods of presenting this information. Economic journalism is another direction gaining prominence in our national journalism. Explaining economic reforms to the wider public, particularly the new economic model of the country—the Strategy of Action for the New Uzbekistan—and clarifying its essence is the main objective of economic journalism. This strategic document also directly addresses information gathering and dissemination, freedom of speech, ensuring transparency of government bodies and organizations, and the development of the journalistic field[1].

Economic journalism is considered one of the leading branches of mass media. In the Russian press, two largely synonymous terms are widely used: “economic journalism” and “business journalism.” In contrast, Western practice more often utilizes the term “business reporting.”

Researchers suggest that there are necessary conditions for differentiating between the concepts of economic and business journalism. The logical basis is that business journalism primarily covers the corporate sector, while the focus and object of study for economic journalism are macroeconomic issues [9, 137]. Studies show that recently, the difference between these terms has gradually diminished, and their meanings have converged. This is a natural process; today, there is no distinction between economic and business journalism in European countries and the USA.

American scholar D. Forsyth traces the history of business journalism back to ancient Babylon and Egypt [5, 1]. However, economic journalism, as a type of mass media, formed much later. In Great Britain and the USA, its development is

typically studied in the following periods:

- 1) First half of the 16th century – mid-18th century;
- 2) Second half of the 18th century – early 20th century;
- 3) 20th century;
- 4) Modern stage (early 21st century).

The rapid development of business journalism in Great Britain is linked to the establishment of The Times. Following this, publications specializing in various sectors of the economy began to emerge. In 1843, The Economist, still considered one of the most prestigious publications today, was launched. At that time, daily financial and economic publications became a new phenomenon in the European market. Competent investors found news from the business world and information on financial matters of interest to them precisely in these economic publications. During this period, Harry Marks (1855-1916), the founder of the Financial Times, significantly influenced the formation of daily business press, becoming "not only a newspaper publisher, but also the founder of a new school in journalism" [3, 35].

The development stages of US business journalism largely mirrored the British experience. Initially, practical journalism emerged, providing information on the prices of raw materials such as cotton, tobacco, and fur. Shortly after the opening of the first factories in the country, the publication New York Price Current was launched. Its success greatly stimulated the creation of the first daily economic newspaper, Daily Items for Merchant (1815). This experience demonstrated the high societal need for business journalism. As a result, by the beginning of the 20th century, the number of economic publications reached 800.

Recent research in Uzbekistan concludes that "despite all existing shortcomings, political and economic journalism exists in the republic," noting that "over 70 business publications have been published in the last twenty-five years," although their appearance is linked to the years of independence [6, 15-16].

Main Part

Although purely economic press emerged as a type of mass media in Uzbekistan in the 21st century, its historical roots and evolution extend far into the past. From this perspective, the formation and development stages of Uzbek business journalism can be conditionally divided into four periods:

1. 5th-8th centuries and later periods;
2. 14th-16th centuries;
3. 20th Century;
4. Years of Independence and the Present Day.

The initial elements of national economic journalism can be traced back to the 5th-8th centuries, in the ancient Turkic written sources such as the Orkhon-Yenisei, Bilge Khagan, and Kül Tigin inscriptions. These inscriptions contain valuable information about trade and economic relations with foreign countries and matters of buying and selling. The Kül Tigin monument is particularly noteworthy as a unique source in this regard, containing the Khagan's appeals to his siblings, relatives, and the people [13, 129-130]. The aim was to prevent internecine conflicts, foster alliances with neighbors, strengthen trade relations, and ultimately achieve prosperity.

The invention of writing and the emergence of written literature marked a turning point in information exchange in the history of human development. In works such as Abu Rayhan Biruni's "India" (1030), Mahmud Kashgari's "Divan Luğati't-Türk" (1077), and Kaykaus's "Qabusnama" (1082-1083), one can observe the early sprouts of journalism. These rare works possess a distinctive publicistic spirit, reflecting the history, economy, life, culture, and daily life of that era. From this perspective, the historical roots of Uzbek journalism extend back a thousand years.

A mature form of economic journalism clearly emerges during the reign of Amir Timur. At that time, the position of "khabarnavis" (news reporter) was

established in every region. Their responsibility was to gather information on the life of the people, the social situation, and the economic state, and to report it daily, weekly, and monthly. "I have ordered that in every place, in the provinces and cities, and in the military camps, reporters (khabarnavis) be appointed to keep me informed about the conduct of the governors, the people, the soldiers, my own troops and foreign troops. They should accurately record for me the goods entering and leaving the country, foreigners entering and leaving, caravans from various countries, news concerning neighboring kings, their words and deeds, and reports concerning scholars and dignitaries who have turned to my court from distant lands" [10, 139]. Reporters were required to report information truthfully without concealing anything and without adding falsehoods. Those found to have violated this faced severe punishment. Those who wrote false reports had their fingers cut off, while those who slandered with malicious intent were executed. Thus, the principles of impartiality and honesty in journalism also have roots in that era.

Financial and economic relations, such as setting monthly salaries and their amounts, tax collection, income distribution, and planned spending, were regulated by Amir Timur. For example, salaries were paid to everyone from ordinary soldiers to commanders, amirs, and governors, according to their decrees. The amount of the salary was written on the back of special decrees.

In collecting taxes and other fees, the economic situation of the population was considered, and in some cases, people were not disturbed for up to three years. Collection was to be carried out "without ruining their condition," through "warnings and explanations, not through beatings and threats". The strict requirement that "any governor whose authority is less effective than that of beating is unfit to govern" [10, 102] became a fundamental criterion in financial and economic relations.

Based on the information in "Timur's Regulations," economic journalism took a definite form in the 14th century, entered a new stage of evolution in the 15th

century, and reached its mature form in terms of content. The influence of the scholars of that time, especially Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, a brilliant scholar in state studies, jurisprudence, history, linguistics, art history, and ethnography, was significant. His work, "Baburnama" (1526-1529), provides valuable information on the socio-economic conditions of the regions he traveled to, ruled, and conquered, as well as their flora, fauna, land, water, and atmosphere.

"His people are Turks. The words of his people are true, written with a pen"[12, 12].

S. Umirov, a dedicated scholar of journalism, described the Baburnama as "a beautiful example of artistic essay writing." "The Baburnama is a wonderful syncretic work that remarkably combines the characteristics and elements of science, art, essay writing, sketches, and essays. The work is a unique and unparalleled example of publicism, more precisely, artistic publicism" [11]. Proof of this can be seen in the description of events of the year 932 (1525-1526) in the work. "On Wednesday, when we stopped at Barikab, Khoja Husayn, the younger brother of Nurbek, who remained in India, brought twenty-five thousand Shahrukh gold ashrafis and coins sent from the Lahore treasury (income). I sent a large part of this money to Balkh for the affairs there through Mulla Ahmad, one of the notables of Balkh"[12, 276].

Furthermore, the work provides economic facts and evidence regarding the economic life, way of life, and sources of income of each region, country, and territory. For example, providing information about Kashmir, he notes, "The wealth of this mountainous people is musk, ambergris, saffron, and copper." He mentions that the livelihood of the population of Kurara and Manikpur is based on elephant hunting, stating, "The price is determined by its size; they sell it according to its height. The larger the elephant, the higher the price." He also discusses the economic culture of the Indian people, subtly highlighting a delicate issue with skill: "In some parts of their fields, there are thickets. The people of these areas hide

in these thickets and refuse to pay taxes."

Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur creatively approached economic themes, presenting economic issues in a language close to journalistic style. As a result, he laid the foundation for many economic terms. The continued use of these terms in our current vocabulary further enhances the value of the Baburnama. As Doctor of Economic Sciences Mafirat Kasimova emphasizes, "the artistic and scientific-artistic works of representatives of Uzbek literature, in particular Alisher Navoi, Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, and others, are unique sources in the development of Uzbek economic terminology" [8].

In our research on the formation of economic journalism, we have witnessed the harmonious development of business press in the region's countries, passing through various stages. The bibliographic indices of E.I. Ivanchikova and S.S. Akasheva contain valuable information in this regard. According to them, before 1917, 27 newspapers and magazines in Russian, with the word "economic" in their titles, were published in the territory of Kazakhstan, Tashkent, Orenburg, and Omsk [7]. However, according to their specialization as "socio-literary and economic newspapers," they did not fully meet the requirements of economic press.

The first purely economic publication in Central Asia is considered to be the journal "Ozbekiston iqtisodiy axborotnomasi"— "Ekonomicheskiy vestnik Uzbekistana". It began publication in Uzbekistan in 1919. During its existence, the journal has been published under six titles and in several tens of millions of copies.

The Jadid press, which generated a new wave in national journalism at the beginning of the last century, ushered in the next period in the development of economic journalism. The issues of national liberation, economic independence, and national progress were the main objectives of daily newspapers such as Taraqqiy, Khursid, Shuhrat, Tujjor, Sadoyi Turkiston, and Samarqand.

Taraqqiy, the first national printed publication, performed the functions of economic journalism to a certain extent. Its pages devoted considerable space to

economic topics.

Taraqqiy newspaper began publication in Tashkent on June 27, 1906, under the editorship of Ismail Obidov. Valuable information about the newspaper can be found on its front page. For example, it stated that this Uzbek-language newspaper for the population of Central Asia, under the name "Taraqqiy," was published twice a week. The column on the right side contained information about the subscription price, while the left column provided the price of advertisements. According to the newspaper, the annual subscription price was 5 rubles, six months was 3 rubles, three months was 1 ruble 40 kopecks, one month was 50 kopecks, and a single issue cost 6 kopecks. Advertisements cost 12 kopecks per line on the first page and 10 kopecks per line on the last page.

In the very first issue of the newspaper, the Jadids criticized the fact that taxes collected from the population were not used for the benefit of the country and people, but were spent on "tyrannical actions and pleasures" [14]. Moreover, small articles published under permanent headings such as "News from Russia," "Domestic News," "Foreign News," "Telegraph News," and "Tashkent News" raised relevant socio-economic issues and provided reasoned criticism of shortcomings. As an example, one can cite the small article "They are making it cheaper for citizens" [14], published under the heading "Various News."

This article analyzes how speculators occupied the markets and arbitrarily inflated the prices of essential daily goods, using the example of charcoal sales, criticizing the suffering of the ordinary population. It calls for clearing the markets of speculators, for people to demand their rights, and for them not to be timid in the face of socio-economic problems, stating, "It is impossible; it is necessary to remove these coal speculators (traders—annotation by S.R.) from the market" [14].

Articles on economic topics in the Jadid press analyzed the extent to which the occurring economic events benefited individuals and society. Authors, standing

for the interests of the people, expressed their opinions and presented their proposals. In an article titled "On the Orenburg-Tashkent old railway," the question is posed: "A straight and close road has been prepared and connected between the Turkestan region and the Russian state. Now we must see what benefits and profits this road will bring to us, the people of Turkestan." It explains that previously, "a large amount of cotton was sent with difficulty to Russian factories and plants," and that, in turn, "when grain was brought from the Russian side via the Caspian Sea and Central Asia railway, grain became very expensive," but now, "since the new railway appeared, grain and crops have become abundant and cheaper in Tashkent" [14].

The sharp critical tone of the articles published in *Taraqiy* was not appreciated by the representatives of the Tsarist Russian colonial regime. After the publication of its nineteenth issue, it was closed down, its editor imprisoned, and its property confiscated. However, such threats and drastic measures did not silence the Jadids. Shortly after, the newspaper *Khursid* began publication under the editorship of M. Abdurashidkhanov. "Khursid began publication using lithography, thanks to the material support of a company formed by the youth of that time after *Taraqiy*'s closure, and under the responsible editorship of Munavvar Qori Abdurashidkhanov" [2], wrote A. Avlooni.

Khursid, and subsequently *Tujjor* and other examples of Jadid press, could not operate for long under colonial persecution. However, the journalistic school, traditions, and rich experience created by these publications formed an important foundation for the development of pure economic journalism at the end of the 19th century and during the years of independence.

Qishloq Hayoti is considered the first economic newspaper in the history of Uzbek journalism. From 1974, it was published under the name *Qishloq Haqiqati*, and until 1989, its Russian-language version, *Sel'skaya Pravda*, was also published. The name of the newspaper was changed to its current name in 1993. As a

publication, it is classified as a "mass socio-economic" newspaper, mainly covering agricultural sectors, rural life, and reforms in agriculture. Therefore, it is not recognized by researchers and scholars as the first Uzbek economic newspaper.

This title is given to Business-Vestnik Vostoka, which began publication in Russian in August 1991. Initially, it was presented as a supplement to the Pravda Vostoka newspaper. From its eighth issue, it was published as an independent weekly newspaper.

This weekly publication for businessmen and entrepreneurs extensively covered the country's economic life, trade, the financial and banking system, enterprises and organizations, as well as the activities of business structures. In particular, it covered business and trade news and advertisements, business advice, information on the Central Asian commodity market, the economic situation in regional countries, and commentaries on relevant laws and regulations. Sufficient space was also allocated to stock exchange bulletins and information. Furthermore, it published materials on important aspects of the economies of near and far foreign countries and on interstate cooperation. For this reason, the newspaper gained readership and subscribers in the CIS and Baltic countries after 2000.

Economic journalism, as a branch of the media system and professional journalistic activity, is striving to become an integral part of the economic infrastructure in Uzbekistan. "Uzbek business press is called upon to effectively meet the audience's need for economic information, to quickly inform about government decisions, and to explain their essence and importance. This aims to make it an intermediary in establishing open dialogue between government bodies and organizations and the population" [6]. However, among some segments of information consumers, the perception persists that economic topics are only for professionals in this field, a narrow circle of specialists. Even for most practicing journalists, economic issues are not particularly interesting.

It's true, as scholars acknowledge, that "writing about economics, informing

the population about it, and raising people's awareness is much more complex than engaging in political maneuvering" [4]. However, economics lies at the heart of human and societal progress. The main task of economic journalism is to actively contribute to promoting a prosperous life by improving people's economic knowledge and skills, enabling them to make sound financial decisions, using financial resources rationally, and reflecting the interests and protection of individuals in the country's economic policy.

Compared to developed countries in Europe and Asia, Uzbekistan has relatively few media outlets that fully meet the requirements of economic journalism. Despite the complex conditions of the "transition period" in the current Uzbek media sphere, those publications that continue to operate are particularly significant in their efforts to advance economic journalism from its formative stage to a stage of development.

Examples of Uzbek economic journalism include newspapers such as Yangi O'zbekiston, Pravda Vostoka, Qishloq Hayoti, Finansovo-ekonomicheskaya gazeta, Bank axborotnomasi/Bankovskie vesti, and Birja; magazines such as Ozbekiston iqtisodiy axborotnomasi (Ekonomicheskii vestnik Uzbekistana), Ekonomicheskoye obozreniye/Iqtisodiy sharh, Hayot va iqtisodiy (Zhizn' i ekonomika), Bozor, pul va kredit (Rynok, den'gi i kredit), and Delovoy partner UZ; as well as news agencies like UzReport, and online publications such as UzDaily.uz, Finance.uz, Kapital.uz, and The Tashkent Times.

Analysis of economic journalism reveals that alongside achievements, certain shortcomings remain. It is premature to say that business publications fully perform their functions. The limited scope of their content, outdated approaches and styles, and the lack of creativity and serious thought among journalists result in a lack of modern spirit in the materials. They fail to provide readers with complete and detailed information about the current economic landscape. The author's position on economic issues is not always evident. In some cases, the expressed

authorial perspective prioritizes the interpretation of the state, government, and authorities, rather than the interests of the population.

Journalism must, first and foremost, reflect the realities of life, prioritize the interests of the people, and actively work to improve people's economic and legal culture. From this perspective, it is regrettable that some economic publications are turning into mere "advertising boards." There are many instances of deviation from the primary function of the press: delivering unbiased information that helps all segments of the population develop financial plans for the near future. Consequently, economic journalism is not advertising or PR. Media outlets with an advertising character must strictly adhere to the requirements that advertising messages should not exceed 40% of the volume of printed publications and 10% of each hour of television and radio programs.

Conclusion

In conclusion, regarding the stages of formation and development, and the functions of economic journalism in Uzbekistan:

First, economic press has traversed a long historical and evolutionary path, becoming an essential component of journalism during the years of independence. More than 70 business publications have been established, and information is disseminated in more than ten languages.

Second, despite some shortcomings in fulfilling their functions, recording contemporary history, and reflecting the realities of life, business publications in the country are progressing from the formation stage to the development stage.

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